

A Comparative Analysis of Recent Tests for Multivariate Normality

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Abstract:

The comparison of several powerful tests for multinormality is appropriate in order to know the test(s) to use under different alternatives to multivariate normality. The aim of this work is to compare the power of some notable powerful multivariate normality tests for different combinations of sample size and variable dimension. The multivariate normality tests considered were Henze and Zirkler test (HZ-test), Szekely and Rizzo energy test (SR-test), Madukaife and Okafor test (MO-test), Henze and Jimenez-Gamero test (HJG-test), Dorr, Ebner and Henze test (DEHU-test), Henze

and Visagie test (HV-test), Ebner, Henz and Strieder test (EHS-test), and Madukaife test (M-test). The study took into account 5 multivariate distributions, 5 different sample sizes ($n = 10, 20, 30, 40$ and 50) and 5 different variable dimensions ($d = 2, 3, 5, 7$ and 9). The multivariate distributions considered were multivariate normal, multivariate t , multivariate uniform, multivariate Laplace, and multivariate exponential distributions. For $2 \leq d \leq 9$, HZ-test, HJG-test, DEHU-test, EHS-test, HV-test, M-test, MO-test and SR-test maintained relevant type-I-error rate under multivariate normal distribution. Under the alternative distributions of multivariate t and Laplace, the MO-test outperformed all the multivariate normality tests at $n = 10, 20, 30, 40$ and 50 regardless of the variable dimension while HZ-test outperformed all the multivariate normality tests at $n = 10, 20, 30, 40$ and 50 regardless of the variable dimension in multivariate uniform distribution. Hence, the MO-test is recommended over HZ-test, HJG-test, DEHU-test, EHS-test, HV-test, M-test and SR-test when the data are asymmetric.

Keywords: *Multivariate normality tests, Type-I-error, Power, Monte Carlo simulation.*

Introduction

Multivariate normality is a fundamental assumption in many multivariate statistical analyses. Testing multivariate normality is a key premise in modern statistical inference. This is due to the fact that many statistical techniques such as multivariate regression, factor analysis, and canonical correlation etc, rely on the assumption of multivariate normality to obtain

unbiased and efficient parameter estimations (Anderson, 2003). Historically, multivariate normality arose as an extension of univariate normality, which is widely recognized and has received substantial research (Pearson, 1919). However, unlike univariate normality which can be assessed visually using histograms or quantile-quantile plots, multivariate normality lacks a simple visual depiction. Mecklin and Mundfrom (2004) have stated that at least 50 different

procedures exist for testing MVN. Since then, several more procedures such as Szekely and Rizzo energy test, Madukaife and Okafor test, Henze and Jimenez-Gamero test and Madukaife test etc, have also been introduced. They are based on various characterizations of the multivariate normal distribution such as measures of skewness and kurtosis, measures of entropy, empirical distribution function, empirical characteristic function, empirical quantile function and various transformation properties of the multivariate normal distribution (Madukaife and Okafor 2018). Although, numerous testing procedures have been proposed to test multinormality, no single test has been shown to be most powerful for all situations. While some tests are affected by sample size, others are affected by the number of variables in the dataset (Bishara & Hittner, 2012). Since parametric tests rely on the assumption of multivariate normality, and multivariate normality tests are affected by sample size and variable dimension, it is appropriate to compare the most powerful multivariate normality tests in terms of type-I-error rate and power in order to validate any of them as the most appropriate in any combinations of sample size and variable dimension. Hence, the purpose of this work is to evaluate the type-I-error rate and power of eight multivariate normality tests under different combinations of sample size and variable dimension.

Methodology

The multivariate normality tests used in this study are discussed in this section.

Henze and Zirkler Test

Henze and Zirkler (1990) obtained a class of affine invariant and consistent test for multivariate normality based on the distance between the empirical characteristic function and the theoretical characteristic function of the multivariate normal distribution. The Henze and Zirkler's statistic for testing the hypothesis of multivariate normality is defined as

$$T_{n,\beta} = n (4I (\mathbf{S} \text{ is singular}) + D_{n,\beta}I (\mathbf{S} \text{ is nonsingular}))$$

Where

$$D_{n,\beta} = \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{j,k=1}^n \exp \left\{ -\frac{\beta^2}{2} \|y_j - y_k\|^2 \right\} - 2(1 + \beta^2)^{-d/2} \frac{1}{n} \quad (1)$$

$$\times \sum_{j=1}^n \exp \left\{ -\frac{\beta^2 \|y_j\|^2}{2(1+\beta^2)} \right\} + (1 + \beta^2)^{-d/2}; y_j = \mathbf{S}^{-1/2}(\mathbf{X}_j - \bar{\mathbf{X}});$$

$I(\cdot)$ is an indicator function and \mathbf{S} is the sample covariance matrix of the multivariate dataset. They recommended the smoothing parameter β to be obtained from kernel density estimation by $\beta = \beta_d(n) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{2d+1}{4} \right)^{\frac{1}{d+4}} n^{\frac{1}{d+4}}$ (Madukaife and Okafor, 2018). The Henze and Zirkler test rejects normality for large values of the test statistic.

Szekely and Rizzo Energy Test

Szekely and Rizzo's statistic for testing the hypothesis of multivariate normality is defined as

$$E N_n = n \left(\frac{2}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \mathbb{E} \|Y_{n,j} - Z\| - \frac{2\Gamma((d+1)/2)}{\Gamma(d/2)} - \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{j,k=1}^n \mathbb{E} \|Y_{n,j} - Y_{n,k}\| \right) \quad (2)$$

Here, the first expectation is with respect to a random vector Z , which is independent of $Y_{n,j}$ and has the distribution $N_d(0, I_d)$ and

$$\mathbb{E} \|a - Z\| = \sqrt{2} \frac{2\Gamma((d+1)/2)}{\Gamma(d/2)} + \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{(-1)^k}{k!2^k} \frac{\|a\|^{2k+2}}{(2k+1)(2k+2)} \times \frac{2\Gamma((d+1)/2)\Gamma(k+1.5)}{\Gamma((d/2)+k+1)} \right\} \quad (3)$$

The Szekely and Rizzo test rejects normality for large values of the test statistic (Szekely and Rizzo, 2005; Henze and Visagie, 2020).

Madukaife and Okafor Test

Madukaife and Okafor's statistic for testing the hypothesis of multivariate normality is defined as

$$T_n = \sum_{i=1}^d \sum_{j=1}^n (z_{i(j)} - c_j)^2 \quad (4)$$

where $c_j; j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ are approximate normal ordered statistics and $z_{i(j); i = 1, 2, \dots, d; j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ are ordered statistics arising from the d principal components transformations of n independent multivariate data set from an unknown multivariate distribution $F(x)$. If the unknown multivariate distribution function $F(x)$ that gave rise to z_{ij} is actually multivariate normal, then it is expected that the statistic T_n will tend to zero. The Madukaife and Okafor test rejects normality for large values of the test statistic (Madukaife and Okafor, 2018).

Henze and Jimenez-Gamero Test

Henze and Jimenez-Gamero (2018) presented a multivariate generalization of a class of tests for univariate normality that is based on the empirical moment generating function. Henze and Jimenez-Gamero's statistic for testing the hypothesis of multivariate normality is defined as

$$H J_n = n \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} (M_n(t) - m(t))^2 \exp(-\beta \|t\|^2) dt, \quad (5)$$

where $\beta > 1$ is a fixed parameter. The test rejects normality for large values of the test statistic (Henze and Visagie, 2020).

Dorr, Ebner and Henze Test

Dorr, Ebner and Henze's statistic for testing the hypothesis of multivariate normality is defined as

$$U_{n,a} = n \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} |\Delta \psi_n(t) - (\|t\|^2 - d) \psi_n(t)|^2 w_a(t) dt, \quad (6)$$

where $w_a(t) = \exp(-a\|t\|^2), t \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and $\psi_n(t) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \exp(it^T Y_{n,j}), t \in \mathbb{R}^d$. The test rejects normality for large values of the test statistic (Dorr et al, 2020).

Henze and Visagie Test

Henze and Visagie's statistic for testing the hypothesis of multivariate normality is defined as

$$T_{n,\gamma} = n \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} \|M'_n(t) - tM_n(t)\|^2 w_\gamma(t) dt, \quad (7)$$

where $w_\gamma(t) = \exp(-\gamma\|t\|^2), t \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and $M_n(t) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n e^{t^T Y_{n,j}}$. The test rejects normality for large values of the test statistic (Henze and Visagie, 2020).

Ebner, Henze and Strieder Test

Ebner, Henze and Strieder's statistic for testing the hypothesis of multivariate normality is defined as

$$T_{n,\gamma} = n \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} |\nabla \psi_n(t) - t\psi_n(t)|_{\mathbb{C}}^2 w_a(t) dt, \quad (8)$$

where $w_a(t) = \exp(-a\|t\|^2), a > 0, t \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and $\psi_n(t) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \exp(it^T Y_{n,j}), t \in \mathbb{R}^d$. The test rejects normality for large values of the test statistic (Ebner et al, 2022).

Madukaife Test

Madukaife (2023) obtained a new Jarque-Bera type statistic for assessing the multivariate normality of a multivariate datasets. Madukaife's statistic for testing the hypothesis of multivariate normality is defined as

$$MAJB_n = \frac{1}{d} \sum_{i=1}^d \left\{ \frac{(\sqrt{b_1})^2}{\text{var}(\sqrt{b_1})} + \frac{(b_2 - E(b_2))^2}{\text{var}(b_2)} \right\} \quad (9)$$

where $\sqrt{b_1} = \frac{\hat{\mu}_3}{\hat{\mu}_2^{3/2}}$ and $b_2 = \frac{\hat{\mu}_4}{\hat{\mu}_2^2}$ are the sample measures of skewness and kurtosis respectively. The test rejects normality for large values of the test statistic (Madukaife, 2023). These tests were chosen from among all the numerous tests for multinormality because Madukaife (2017) affirmed that these multivariate normality tests are among the most powerful tests for MVN in the literature.

Monte Carlo Simulation

The Monte Carlo simulation was conducted in order to compare the power performance of the multivariate normality tests for various combinations of sample size and variable dimension. The power performance of HZ-test, HJG-test, DEHU-test, EHS-test, HV-test, M-test, MO-test and SR-test were evaluated under 5 variable dimensions ($d = 2, 3, 5, 7$ and 9) for various sample sizes ($n = 10, 20, 30, 40$ and 50). The multivariate standard normal distribution was used for the scenarios under which normality assumption holds while multivariate t , multivariate uniform, multivariate Laplace and multivariate exponential distributions were used for the scenarios under which normality assumption was violated. The R statistical package was used to implement the Monte Carlo technique sampling of 10,000 multivariate datasets of each distribution. In each distribution, the simulated data were analyzed appropriately using the HZ-test, HJG-test, DEHU-test, EHS-test, HV-test, M-test, MO-test and SR-test in order to obtain the power. The power of a test is the ability of the test to reject a false null hypothesis. It can be obtained theoretically when the null distribution is known and empirically when it is unknown (Madukaife and Okafor, 2018). The comparison procedures were considered in two categories. Firstly, if the null hypothesis (H_0 : The data were sampled from multivariate normal distribution) was true, the rejection rate of the null hypothesis was considered as the type-I-error rate for each test. The test that has the closest type-I-error to the nominal α , where $\alpha = 0.05$ would be considered to be more robust in terms of type-I-

error. Secondly, if the alternative hypothesis (H_1 : The data were not sampled from multivariate normal distribution) was true, the rejection rate of the null hypothesis was considered as the power for each test. The test that has the largest power would be taken to be most powerful test.

Results

The powers of some multivariate normality tests were computed and compared for various combinations of sample size (n) and different variable dimensions (d). They are presented in Tables 1-5 for $d = 2, 3, 5, 7$ and 9 respectively. The values in bold in Tables 1-5 denote the best power performance at any given combinations of sample size and variable dimension under an alternative distribution. Under the null distribution of multivariate normality, it is observed from Tables 1 – 5 that the power of all the multivariate normality tests had no specific pattern for all the various combinations of variable dimension and sample size. Under $d = 2$, HJG-test, DEHU-test, EHS-test, EHS-test, HV-test and MO-test were observed to have a good control over type-I-error for $n = 10$. While all the tests had good control over type-I-error at $n = 20$ under $d = 2$, M-test was the only test that had good control over type-I-error for $20 \leq n \leq 40$. For $n = 50$, MO-test and SR-test were the only tests that had good control over type-I-error under $d = 2$. Under $d = 3$, DEHU-test, EHS-test, EHS-test and HV-test were observed to have a good control over type-I-error for $n = 10$. While all the tests had good control over type-I-error for $30 \leq n \leq 40$ and $d = 3$, HZ-test, DEHU-test, EHS-test, M-test and SR-test had good control over type-I-error at $d(n) = 3(50)$. Under $d = 5$, the type-I-error rate of HZ-test, DEHU-test, EHS-test and SR-test were greater than 0.05 for $10 \leq n \leq 40$ while M-test, MO-test, HV-test and SR-test had good control over type-I-error at $n = 20, 30, 40$ and 50 respectively. Under $d = 7$, the type-I-error rate of HZ-test, MO-test and SR-test were less than 0.05 for $10 \leq n \leq 30$ while EHS-test and M-test had good control over type-I-error at $n = 30, 40$ and 50 . Under $d = 9$, M-test and MO-test were observed to have a good control over type-I-error for $n =$

10. While HZ-test had good control over type-I-error at $n = 20$ under $d = 2$, MO-test was the only test that had good control over type-I-error for $30 \leq n \leq 40$. Since the null hypothesis is true under multivariate normality, the power of all the multivariate normality tests is the type-I-error rate. Furthermore, the power of all the multivariate normality tests was approximately 0.05 except at $d = 9$, where M-test and HZ-test were approximately 0.04 and 0.06 at $n = 10$ and $n = 40$ respectively. Under the alternative distribution of multivariate t , it is observed from Tables 1-5 that the power of all the multivariate normality tests increased as the sample size increased under each variable dimension. For $10 \leq n \leq 50$, the power of all the tests was observed to increase as the variable dimension increased. From the results, MO-test yielded the power value of 1 for all the various combinations of variable dimension and sample size. Furthermore, the power of other multivariate normality tests was inferior to that of MO-test for $n = 10$ under $d = 9$. Although, all the multivariate normality tests were observed to be powerful for sample sizes between 30 and 50, MO-test was observed to be the most powerful test for $10 \leq n \leq 50$ regardless of variable dimension.

Under the alternative distribution of multivariate uniform, it is observed from Tables 1-5 that the power of HZ-test increases as the sample size increases under each variable dimension while the power of all other multivariate normality tests had no specific pattern for all the various combinations of variable dimension and sample size. From the results, the power of HZ-test was observed to decrease as the variable dimension increases except for $n = 10$ under $d = 9$. Under $d = 2, 3, 5, 7$ and 9 , HZ-test was observed to be the most powerful test for $10 \leq n \leq 50$ except for $n = 10$ under $d = 9$, where the powers of HJG-test, DEHU-test, EHS-test and HV-test were at par with that of HZ-test.

Under the alternative distribution of multivariate Laplace, it is observed from Tables 1-5 that the power of all the multivariate normality tests increases as the sample size increases under each variable dimension. For $10 \leq n \leq 50$, the power of all the tests was observed to increase as the

variable dimension increases. From the results, MO-test yielded the power value of 1 for all the various combinations of variable dimension and sample size. Furthermore, the power of other multivariate normality tests was inferior to that of MO-test for $n = 10$ under $d = 9$. Although, all the multivariate normality tests were observed to be powerful for sample sizes between 30 and 50, MO-test was observed to be the most powerful test for $10 \leq n \leq 50$ regardless of variable dimension.

Under the alternative distribution of multivariate exponential, it is observed from Tables 1-5 that the power of all the multivariate normality tests increases as the sample size increases under each variable dimension. Under $d = 2$, EHS-test was observed to be the most powerful test for sample sizes between 30 and 50 while HZ-test and SR-test performed better than EHS-test at $n = 10$ and $n = 20$ respectively. Under $d = 3$, SR-test was observed to be the most powerful test for sample sizes of 10, 20, 40 and 50 while EHS-test performed better than SR-test at $n = 30$ and were at par with SR-test at $n = 50$. Under $d = 5$, M-test was observed to be the most powerful test for $10 \leq n \leq 50$. However, EHS-test were at par with M-test at $n = 50$. Under $d = 7$, M-test was observed to be the most powerful test for $10 \leq n \leq 50$. However, EHS-test and SR-test were at par with M-test at $n = 50$. Under $d = 9$, M-test was observed to be the most powerful test for $20 \leq n \leq 50$. However, MO-test performed better than M-test at $n = 10$ while EHS-test and SR-test were at par with M-test at $n = 50$.

Discussion of Results

The comparison of several powerful tests for multinormality is appropriate in order to know the test(s) to use under different alternatives to multivariate normality. HZ-test, HJG-test, DEHU-test, EHS-test, HV-test, M-test, MO-test and SR-test are statistical tests that can be used to test for multinormality. In determining the appropriate test to use for various combinations of variable dimension and sample size, the power performance of these multivariate normality tests was compared under

$2 \leq d \leq 9$ for $10 \leq n \leq 50$ in several multivariate distributions.

For $d = 2$, the MO-test outperformed all other multivariate normality tests when the data were sampled from multivariate t and multivariate Laplace distributions while HZ-test and EHS-test outperformed the MO-test under multivariate uniform and multivariate exponential distributions respectively. Under $d = 2$, the M-test had more control of type-I-error rates than all the multivariate normality tests for sample sizes between 20 and 40 while the EHS-test and the MO-test had more control of type-I-error rates than M-test for sample sizes of 10 and 50 respectively. Although, the EHS-test outperformed the MO-test in multivariate exponential distribution under $d = 2$, the SR-test outperformed EHS-test for sample sizes of 20 and 50 under multivariate exponential distribution.

For $d = 3$, the MO-test outperformed all other multivariate normality tests when the data were sampled from multivariate t and multivariate Laplace distributions while HZ-test and SR-test outperformed the MO-test under multivariate uniform and multivariate exponential distributions respectively. Under $d = 3$, the M-test had more control of type-I-error rates than all the multivariate normality tests for sample sizes of 30 and 50 while the EHS-test, the MO-test and HZ-test had more control of type-I-error rates than M-test for sample sizes of 10, 20 and 40 respectively. Although the SR-test outperformed the MO-test in multivariate exponential distribution under $d = 3$, the EHS-test were at par with SR-test for sample sizes of 30 and 50 under multivariate exponential distribution.

For $d = 5$, the MO-test outperformed all other multivariate normality tests when the data were sampled from multivariate t and multivariate Laplace distributions while HZ-test and M-test outperformed the MO-test under multivariate uniform and multivariate exponential distributions respectively. Under $d = 5$, the M-test had more control of type-I-error rates than all the multivariate normality tests for $n \leq 20$ while the MO-test, HV-test and SR-test had

more control of type-I-error rates than M-test for sample sizes of 30, 40 and 50 respectively. Although, the M-test outperformed the MO-test in multivariate exponential distribution under $d = 5$, the EHS-test were at par with M-test for $n = 50$ under multivariate exponential distribution.

For $d = 7$, the HZ-test had more control of type-I-error rates than all the multivariate normality tests for $n \leq 20$ while the MO-test, HJG-test and EHS-test had more control of type-I-error rates than HZ-test for sample sizes of 30, 40 and 50 respectively. Under $d = 7$, the M-test outperformed all the multivariate normality tests when the data were sampled from multivariate exponential distribution while the EHS-test and SR-test were at par with M-test at $n = 50$ under multivariate exponential distribution. Although MO-test outperformed all other multivariate normality tests in multivariate t and multivariate Laplace distributions under $d = 7$, DEHU-test, EHS-test and SR-test were at par with MO-test at $n = 50$ in multivariate t distribution while DEHU-test and SR-test were at par with MO-test at $n = 50$ in multivariate Laplace distribution.

Under $d = 9$, the MO-test had more control of type-I-error rates than all the multivariate normality tests for $30 \leq n \leq 50$ while the M-test and HZ-test had more control of type-I-error rates than HZ-test for sample sizes of 10 and 20 respectively. For $d = 9$, the M-test outperformed all the multivariate normality tests when the data were sampled from multivariate exponential distribution while the EHS-test and SR-test were at par with M-test at $n = 50$ under multivariate exponential distribution. Under $d = 9$, MO-test outperformed all other multivariate normality tests in multivariate t and multivariate Laplace distributions for $10 \leq n \leq 30$. While all the tests remained relevant type-I-error rates under multivariate normal distribution, the HZ-test and SR-test were the only tests that were not approximately powerless under multivariate uniform distribution.

Conclusion

This work compared the type-I-error rate and power of several multivariate normality tests for

various combinations of sample size and variable dimension. The power of all the multivariate normality tests had no specific pattern for all the various of sample size and variable dimension under multivariate normal and uniform distribution. For $2 \leq d \leq 9$, the power of all the multivariate normality tests increases as sample size increases under multivariate t , multivariate Laplace and multivariate exponential distributions. All the tests except the HZ-test and SR-test were approximately powerless under multivariate uniform distribution. Although MO-test had the power value of 1 under multivariate t and multivariate Laplace distributions, the power of the other tests approaches 1 as the sample sizes increases for $2 \leq d \leq 9$ in multivariate t and multivariate Laplace distributions. Regardless of variable dimension and sample size, the MO-test was observed to be the most powerful test under multivariate t and multivariate Laplace distributions while the HZ-test was observed to be the most powerful test under multivariate uniform distribution. The EHS-test, SR-test and M-test were more powerful than HZ-test, HJG-test, DEHU-test, HV-test and MO-test under multivariate exponential distribution. Based on the conclusions from the results obtained in this work, the MO-test is recommended over HZ-test, HJG-test, DEHU-test, EHS-test, HV-test, M-test and SR-test when the data are asymmetric. In symmetric distributions, HZ-test and SR-test should be used for the test for multinormality since HJG-test, DEHU-test, EHS-test, HV-test, M-test and MO-test were approximately powerless under multivariate uniform distribution. For future work, these multivariate normality tests should be considered under skewed distributions such as multivariate beta, multivariate Cauchy, multivariate logistic distributions to see if similar results would be obtained using these combinations of sample size and variable dimension.

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